

APPROACHES OF COGNITIVE LINGUISTICS

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Annotation: For decades, Cognitive Linguistics (CL) has drawn scholars' impeccable attention in all fields from different aspects since the significance of this topic could urge them to work on and analyze shreds of evidence and findings in order to reach a bold destination. An introductory chapter provides deep insights to explore essential topics that are linked to this term directly and indirectly with relevant experiences. Furthermore, the article explores the significance of bi/multilingualism in cognitive linguistics considering high-quality research papers that can assist to clues.

Keywords: Cognitive linguistics, bi/multilingualism, Linguistic imperialism.

It is undeniable that English can assist in the integration of cultures which results in creating multicultural dimensions because any language is part of any nation which has been ensured for ages. At this point, it can be worthwhile to think about the circles that Kachru (1990) provided us with exclusive findings from his treasure. According to this perspective, the users of English in the world are divided into three categories considering the history of each country. Specifically, three groups: Inner Circle, Outer Circle, and Expanding Circle got their names due to their history. For instance, England colonized India many centuries ago and established their culture and language to build a government. So, India is now an outer circle since the English language has maintained its formality and globality for many years. In the Inner Circle, there are the USA, UK, Canada, Australia, and New Zealand where the formal language is English. Other countries like Uzbekistan are in the Expanding circle and English is taught as a foreign language. Nowadays the volume of acquiring English is accelerating from time to time since English is a lingua franca which is a trigger to success for learners. For instance, In Uzbekistan, English is a good way to gain prosperity by assimilating into developed countries, implementing breakthroughs, and absorbing models so as to generate discoveries. However, assimilation is not only seen in education, political system, medicine, pharmacy, heavy industry, and others, but also in cultural insights, traditions and customs, and even traits and behaviors.

Kachru (1990) emphasized the varieties and changes that can be applied in countries where English is spoken. This means that English is taught internationally which can result in variations and alterations in this language

due to the diversity in terms of pronunciations, accents, and dialects. There is one concern that might be triggered by the intensity of the changes in English that make some words dead and expansions of English vocabulary with new words. As a matter of fact, there are overwhelming languages that are connected with cultures religious aspects, and traditions globally which can be the main enhancement of the English dictionary by transferring or identifying the equivalent of the words if they exist. If it is not some words may widen English vocabulary since any language is in the process of increase or decrease which brings them to rebuild or die-dead languages academically.

Nowadays the term “Linguistic imperialism” is being used in linguistics as a means of dominant language. Making language a Lingua Franca can be associated not only with the linguistic factors that link expansion and the connections of interlanguages but also with political and economic dominance and establishment play an integral role in enabling over ranking of the language. Linguistic imperialism can lower the status of other languages and ultimately pose to the intensification of processes out of use. As for circles, all humans, whether they are in linguistics or not have inclinations in terms of acquiring a dominant language since there are economic, educational, and technological dependence.

Pervaiz et al. (2019) put high emphasis on linguistic imperialism, which has a direct link to sociopolitical phenomena that originated due to colonization. The term “Linguistic imperialism” was coined By Phillipson in 1992, which brought the emergence of hot debates in linguistics (**Pervaiz et al., 2019**).

However, any language itself is the reflection of cognitive conceptualization which embodies the process of synthesizing, analyzing, and generating the idea appropriately. According to **Croft and Cruse (2006)**, language is not sovereign and needs to be enriched and boosted. Language has always relied on situations that can assist in enhancing and enriching the movements.

To sum up, cognitive linguistics is the field of exploring the relations between humans and their language usage. Cognition is pertinent to the humans’ competence, ability, social relations, and experiences since biological and medical well-being stand in front of cognitive linguistics.

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